

COMPREHENSIVE RISK ASSESSMENT OF FLOODS IN CYPRUS: EVALUATING THE IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

In the context of natural disasters, floods are the leading cause of death and building damage on European territory. These phenomena manifest themselves as flooding over a short period of time in generally dry areas, and are therefore characterized by very high velocity transport of matter (mainly water), sometimes accentuated by the orography of the affected area. The island of Cyprus is geographically located in a semi – arid region but due to climate change, sudden and very heavy rains can occur, causing damage. In addition, in the past there was no regulation on construction in flood-prone areas, and the building expansion of the early '80s to the late '90s has greatly increased the risk of damage due to the increase in exposed property. Although the occurrence of flood events has highlighted the island's fragility to the phenomenon, and the Cypriot state has enacted structural adjustment regulations in the field of construction, the amount of exposed property and the time it takes to adjust remains very high. Furthermore, in most towns in Cyprus, property losses occur almost every year due to poor maintenance of infrastructure. In this paper, a review research was conducted on the current knowledge on the subject, especially for the floods in Cyprus, reflecting on current gaps in risk assessment and needs to improve flood-resilient planning and design for local infrastructure and communities.

Keywords: Climate Change, Floods, Hazards, Natural-based Mitigation Measures, Cyprus

INTRODUCTION

Regions with arid and semiarid climates experience both prolonged droughts and flash floods, which affect the economy, people's lives, and the environment [1]. Even in recent years, floods in these arid areas have resulted in many deaths and large economic losses. Recent data from Cyprus, for example, show a decrease in rainfall. Climate change is exacerbating extreme weather events in these areas, like heavy rain, high temperatures, and long droughts and increasing the likelihood of severe flooding in the future. This problem is made worse by growing populations and human activities like city expansion, wrong land use, economic growth, and lack of awareness.

Besides climate change and human activity, several unique factors make dry areas more prone to severe flooding and unexpected flood damage. The wide variety in climate, geography, rocks, plants, and water systems in these areas makes it hard for local flood managers to do their job [2]. On the other hand, challenges related to humans and systems, such as focusing too much on managing drought and not having the right institutional frameworks, negatively affect Flood Risk Management (FRM).

All these points highlight the need for a better understanding of FRM challenges in dry areas to reduce the negative effects of floods on the environment, economy, and society—now and in the future.

Therefore, this review will first look at the relationship between temperature and rain over the last 30 years in Cyprus, classify floods by how severe they are using data collected since 1859, identify the most common flood types on the island, and suggest some nature-based solutions that can be easily adopted by both the community and individuals.

THE SCENARIO OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN CYPRUS

Cyprus faces several climate risks (Table 1) and the search for efficient, acceptable solutions is a priority [3]. Each risk leads to numerous negative impacts on human well-being and environmental health, ecosystem biodiversity, agriculture, tourism, energy demand and supply, and generally all sectors of society and the economy.

Table 1. Table in relation to climate risks in Cyprus

Type of Climate Risk	Current Level risk	Expected change in Intensity	Expected change in Frequency	Timeline	Indicators relating to the Risks
Extreme Rainfall	Moderated	Increase	Increase	Medium term	Increase of days with intense precipitation (associated with flooding)
Floods	High	Increase	Increase	Medium term	Increase in flooding from rivers and rains
Storms	Moderated	Increase	Increase	Long term	Increase in exceptional phenomena in recent years
Coastal Erosion	Mediocre	Increase	Increase	Medium term	Increase in coastal erosion and the resulting salinization of the water table
Heat wave	High	Increase	Increase	Present	Increase in the frequency and duration of heat waves

Drought	High	Increase	Increase	Present	Increase in days without rainfall (2020-2050)
Dust	High	Increase	Increase	Present	Increase in dust levels

Climate in Cyprus is expected to change in the next few years with rising of the local temperatures along with other adverse effects. Geographically located in the Middle East, Cyprus faces a future with high temperatures and less rainfall which will accelerate the island’s desertification [4]. These weather conditions will, in the future, probably affect the people and some other sectors such as the food production, the water availability, the tourism and the urban and rural societies because of the great intensity of heat waves.

Average temperatures in Cyprus could rise significantly, by about 1 to 3°C over the next three decades, 3°C to 5°C by mid-century, and 3.5°C to 7°C by the end of the century [5]. This could lead to a two-week increase in the number of hot days in Cyprus exceeding 38°C between 2020 and 2050. In 2019, for example, Nicosia had 12 days with temperatures exceeding 38°C. By 2050, Nicosia could experience about 24 such days, an increase of more than 100%. Cyprus will also experience 30 additional warm tropical nights above 25°C than is currently the case. In 2019, Nicosia experienced 6 nights where the temperature was above or equal to 25°C, one month longer than today. By 2050, Nicosia could experience 36 such nights, a 600% increase. Half of these warm tropical nights also had daytime temperatures above 38°C. This means that Nicosia could experience 18 days of incredibly high daytime temperatures in 2050, with no relief at sunset.

Figure 1. Relationship of Temperature - Precipitation in Cyprus

Figure 1 shows the change in maximum temperature on the island and precipitation from 1901 to 2021. Over the years, the average value of precipitation decreases, while the opposite trend follows that of the maximum temperature per year. According to history.com [6], the early 1980s would mark a sharp rise in global temperatures. Many pundits, such as Nasa scientist James Hansen, point to 1988 as a critical turning

point, as turning events brought global warming into the spotlight. Something similar can be observed in the case of Cyprus as shown in the chart below where we have the intersection of the two lines.

The average annual precipitation between 1991 - 2021 (461.71 mm) is about 3% lower than the average annual precipitation between 1961 - 1990 (476.4 mm) and is the lowest in a recorded 30-year period. The average annual precipitation between 1931 - 1960 is 470 mm, and the average annual precipitation between 1901 - 1930 was the highest at 520 mm. The most recent 30-year period was the driest [7], however there were some very extreme events such as the 2012 precipitation of 711 mm and 2019 (Figure 2), the wettest year since 1968, with 631 mm, followed by floods and natural disasters.

Figure 2. Annual Precipitation in Cyprus

FLOODING IN CYPRUS

Flooding is a natural phenomenon that takes place when the level of a water body begins to rise to the point where it overflows its artificial embankments or natural banks, submerging normally dry areas [8]. The four most common types of floods that someone can encounter in Cyprus are the following;

- Fluvial flood, also known as a river flood, happens when the water level in a river or lake increases and spills over onto the nearby coastlines, banks, and land,
- Pluvial flood, when there is a flood without an overflowing water body, it is called a pluvial or surface water flood,
- Flash flooding, are caused by extreme rainfall events or the sudden release of water over a short period of time and
- Coastal flooding, the flooding of coastal areas by seawater usually caused by high tide, tsunamis, and storm surge.

The following tables provide statistics for all recorded 615 flood events that occurred during the period 1859 - 2021. Most of these events (429) were recorded after 1991. Statistical analysis shows that both the type of floods and their severity are distributed as follows in each 30-year period recorded.

Table 2. Flood rates by severity per 30 year period

Period	Severity
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	<i>Very Low</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>High</i>	<i>Very High</i>
2021 - 1991	50.3	28.4	19.3	1.9	0.0
1990 - 1961	36.8	43.9	8.8	10.5	0.0
1960 - 1931	37.5	18.8	43.8	0.0	0.0
1930 - 1901	17.9	43.6	28.2	7.7	2.6
1900 - 1859	15.8	57.9	15.8	5.3	5.3

Table 3. Flood types per 30 year period.

Period	Flood Type		
	<i>Fluvial</i>	<i>Pluvial</i>	<i>Flash</i>
2021 - 1991	22.4	58.3	19.3
1990 - 1961	19.3	67.5	13.2
1960 - 1931	25.0	18.8	56.3
1930 - 1901	23.7	0.0	76.3
1900 - 1859	33.3	0.0	66.7

An interesting statistic in Table 2 shows that between 1931 and 1960, most floods (43.8%) were of medium severity. In the 1961-1990 period, the percentage with low severity predominated (43.9%), while it continued to improve in recent years (50.3%).

The above percentages (Table 3) are consistent with the fact that floods in the Cypriot region are usually characterized as pluvial floods (58.3%, in the last 30 years), due to extensive urbanization combined with flash floods, which are likely to cause more intense direct damage than other types of floods due to the small size of the watersheds, steepness of the land, low vegetation, high rainfall intensity, and short concentration time (e.g. Fluvial flooding).

Until 2014, Cyprus did not have a flood risk plan. Currently, Cyprus has identified 38 (19 areas before 2011 and 19 by 2018) Areas of Potentially Significant Flood Risk (APSFRs) under the Flood Directive. As stated, 5,370 people are currently exposed to significant flood risk at a frequency of 5% (T=20 years) according to the preliminary flood risk management plan [9]. Urbanization will increase this number to 15,170.

The Water Development Department (WDD) of Cyprus has created and posted online Interactive Flood Risk Maps [10] so that every citizen can immediately see the existence or non-existence of a potential flood risk and the possible extent of flooding of their property by entering information such as e.g. the street or parcel number of his property through a GIS platform.

The Flood Hazard Maps (Figure 3) show the area that could be covered by water and the depth of water for 3 different flooding scenarios:

1. A low probability flood (1 in 500).

2. A medium probability flood (1 in 100).
3. A flood with a high probability (1 in 20).

Figure 3. Interactive Flood Hazard Maps

NATURAL-BASED MITIGATION MEASURES

In light of escalating climate challenges, societies globally have recognized the imperative need to reassess traditional flood mitigation measures. Historically, flood risk reduction has predominantly focused on hard engineering solutions. However, the unpredictable intensities and patterns of precipitation, as influenced by climate change, necessitate a paradigm shift in our approach to flood management.

The current era of flood mitigation strategies emphasizes sustainability combined with environmental harmony. The convergence of gray (traditional engineering) and green (nature-based) infrastructure represents this new direction. Presented below are a few nature-based measures epitomizing this evolution:

Permeable Materials: These are non-sealed surfaces designed to allow water absorption, offering an alternative to the conventional sealed surfaces. Sealed surfaces often intensify urban flooding, inhibit the formation of local ecosystems, and escalate the urban heat island effect.

Benefits:

- Significantly reduce flooding potential by absorbing 80-100% of water during intense rainfall, cutting back on property damage and preventing soil erosion.
- With increased rainwater infiltration capacity, permeable materials enhance groundwater, helping to save water, especially in times of drought..

Rain Gardens: These specially designed gardens act as natural reservoirs, collecting rainwater and reducing its flow in urban settings.

Benefits:

- Mitigate flooding from excessive rainfall and retain pollutants.
- Control the urban heat island effect.

Tree Planting: An elemental yet potent nature-based solution, increasing vegetation counters several environmental challenges.

Benefits:

- Promote water retention and filtration.
- Aid in soil retention.

Roof Gardens: These are vegetative layers on building rooftops, established over a structured sequence of layers including waterproofing, anti-root protection, moisture retention substrate, drainage, and growth substrate.

Benefits:

- Substantially decrease heating expenses due to added thermal insulation provided by the vegetation layer.
- Reduce summer cooling costs by up to 49% through solar energy reflection and absorption by the plants.
- Enhance urban air quality by oxygen production, carbon dioxide absorption, and pollutant uptake.
- Diminish noise pollution and further alleviate the urban heat island effect.
- Achieve a 40-80% decrease in rainwater runoff into sewers due to the absorption capacity of rooftop plants.
- Offer an avenue to reintroduce greenery in urban settings, potentially serving as habitats for local biodiversity.

CONCLUSION

The expected changes in Cyprus' climate, including higher local temperatures and less yearly rainfall, are likely to significantly affect the island's risk to flooding. A clear change in weather patterns has been noticed, mainly seen as a drop in rainfall volume. At the same time, the lack of proper maintenance or inadequate flood protection systems makes flooding problems worse, causing various issues in both city and countryside areas. The government has started projects like creating interactive flood hazard maps and improving infrastructure to tackle these problems. Moreover, a key role is also seen for the people of Cyprus, whose adoption of eco-friendly practices could greatly help these mitigation efforts. Community-driven actions such as setting up rain gardens, planting trees, creating roof gardens, and using permeable materials are recognized as good strategies. These actions not only help individuals but also contribute to a group effort in reducing the risks from heavy rain floods. Through a combined approach involving government action and citizen participation, there's a hopeful path towards reducing the negative effects of climate change on flood hazard vulnerability in Cyprus.

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